

Road Traffic Analysis Using Yolo-V4 & Deepsort

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Abstract--As the number of people and cars in cities increases, one of the main problems is becoming traffic congestion. In addition to making driving more stressful and time-consuming, traffic bottlenecks also burn more petrol and pollute the air. Despite the fact that it appears to be everywhere, megacities are the ones most impacted by it. Because of this, it is also becoming more and more important to compute the road traffic density in real-time in order to improve signal control and manage traffic. Among the key elements influencing traffic flow is the traffic controller. Consequently, in order to better meet this growing demand, traffic control must be optimised. With the use of image processing and artificial intelligence, our suggested method would calculate traffic density based on real-time photos from traffic junction cameras. In order to ease traffic and minimise pollution, it also focuses on the algorithm that changes traffic signals according to the density of vehicles.

Keywords: Traffic, Density, traffic flow, YOLO Object.

I. INTRODUCTION

India's population is growing four times slower than its traffic. These days, a great number of nations struggle with traffic congestion, which seriously impairs urban transit. Even with automated traffic systems taking the role of traffic cops and custodians, optimising traffic congestion remains a major challenge, particularly in areas with multiple intersection nodes. In addition to causing traffic jams, additional serious difficulties arise from them that directly impact people's daily lives and occasionally result in fatalities, such as when an ambulance or other emergency vehicle is travelling on a road with a critically ill patient. There's a good risk the patient won't make it to the hospital in time if the ambulance gets caught in heavy traffic in such scenario. In order to prevent accidents, crashes, and traffic congestion, it is imperative to design a sophisticated traffic system that intelligently directs traffic. When two paths have equal amounts of traffic but different green light durations, it is wasteful and a waste of time when one path has less traffic than the other. Taking into account the example above, the path with more traffic should glow greener than the path with less traffic for a longer amount of time. The basis of this method is the correlation between a reference image and the live traffic image to calculate the traffic density. The main distinction is the noticeable increase in traffic density. However, because so many different factors are involved, the traffic problem is extremely complex[1]. First, the flow of traffic is determined by the time of day, with morning and afternoon hours typically seeing the most traffic. Weekends tend to have the least amount of traffic, whereas Mondays and Fridays typically have a lot of traffic heading from cities to their outskirts and the other way around, respectively, as well as throughout the autumn and summer seasons. Second, modern traffic signal systems are implemented with hard coded delays, meaning that the times at which the light turns on and off are often fixed and independent of actual traffic volume. The third point relates to how one light junction's condition affects how traffic moves through nearby intersections. Additionally, a critical concern of the overall traffic system is the efficient flow of emergency vehicles with higher priority through intersections, including ambulances, rescue vehicles, fire engines, police, and VIPs who might be targeted by the mob. In order to reduce traffic volume and waiting times, ease transportation issues, reduce overall travel time, and increase the benefits to the economy, environment, and public health, the regular traffic system must be improved. In order to overcome numerous flaws and enhance traffic management, this study suggests a straight forward, low-cost traffic signal control system[2].

II. PROBLEMSTATEMENT

The congestion of urban traffic is turning into one among the important problems with increasing population and vehicles in cities. Traffic jams not only cause further delay and stress for the drivers, how ever additionally increase fuel consumption, add transportation prices, and increase pollution[3]. though it looks to interpenetrate very place, mega cities area unit those most stricken by it. And it's increasing nature makes it imperative to understand the road traffic density in period of time for higher signal management and effective traffic management[4]. The traffic controller is one in every of the important factors touching traffic flow. This traffic management systems that are in place area unit usually static, which implies that they do not regulate per the requirements of the traffic flow.

III. PROPOSEDSYSTEM

Our proposed system aims to present a traffic light controller based on Computer Vision that can adapt to the current traffic situation. It uses live video feed from the CCTV cameras at traffic junctions for real-time traffic density calculation by detecting the vehicles at the signal and setting the green signal time accordingly[5]. The vehicles are classified as car, bus/truck, or rickshaw to obtain a more accurate estimate of the green signal time. We have used object detection like computer vision in order to detect the number of vehicles for each direction. We then set the timers of these traffic signals according to vehicle density in each direction and hence the system becomes adaptive. This helps to optimize the green signal times, and traffic is cleared at a far quicker rate than a static system, therefore reducing the unwanted delays, congestion, and waiting time, which in turn will reduce the fuel consumption and pollution.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Now-a-days due to increasing number of vehicles it's becoming difficult to manage traffic efficiently which leads to longer duration journey and maximum petrol consumption and to avoid this problem standard techniques was introduce such as manual traffic control which require more number of traffic person, static time traffic control which is not effective as it will use same timer for all lanes with heavy and light traffic and sensor based traffic management but this require heavy budge to f sensor deployment to sense and manage traffic . To overcome from above issues author of this paper is utilizing traffic cameras and YOLO object detection algorithms to estimate traffic density at all lanes and then adjusted and green signal time[6]. Cameras will take snap shot of all lanes every five seconds and then estimate traffic at lanes and based on density green and red signal time will be adjusted. The number of vehicles of each class, such as car, bike, bus, and truck, is detected, which is to calculate the density of traffic. The signals witching algorithm muses this density, among some other factors, to set the green signal timer for each lane. There signal times are updated accordingly. The green signal time is restricted to a maximum and minimum value in order to avoid starvation of a particular lane. A simulation is also developed to demonstrate the system's effectiveness and compare it with the existing static system

Fig. 1 System Architecture

V. RESULTS

Fig. 2 .TRAFFIC DENSITY CALCULATION SYSTEM

In above screen you can see PYGAME simulation output and at each lane traffic density is calculated and then adjust green and red line. This simulation run in INFINITE loop so you press 'windows' key from keyboard and then close application and then restart and run second YOLO module[7][8].

Now in above screen click on 'Run YoloTraffic Detection & Counting' button to upload traffic video and then estimate traffic density. In above screen selecting and uploading 'traffic2.mp4' video and then click on 'Open' button to get below output

Fig. 3 .Traffic Detection & Counting Image

In above screen detecting traffic and then estimating its count and based on that traffic time will be adjusted. YOLO runs very slowly in normal laptop so let it finish all frame processing then you will get output.mp4 file which you can play as normal video with traffic density.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the proposed system sets the green signal time adaptively according to the traffic density at the signal and ensures that the direction with more traffic is allotted a green signal for a longer duration of time as compared to the direction with lesser traffic. This will lower the unwanted delays and reduce congestion and waiting time, which in turn will reduce fuel consumption and pollution. According to simulation results, the system shows about 23% improvement over the current system in terms of the number of vehicles crossing the intersection, which is a significant improvement. With further calibration using real-life CCTV data for training the model, this system can be improved to perform even better.

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VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Tom.com, 'TomTom World Traffic Index', 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.tomtom.com/en_gb/traffic-index/ranking/
- [2] Khushi, "Smart Control of Traffic Light System using Image Processing," 2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC), Mysore, 2017, pp. 99-103, doi:10.1109/CTCEEC.2017.8454966.
- [3] A. Vogel, .Ivanjko, "Improving Traffic Light Control by Means of Fuzzy Logic," 2018 International Symposium ELMAR, Zadar, 2018, pp. 51-56, doi:10.23919/ELMAR.2018.8534692
- [4] Choi A. A. Zaid, Y. Suhweil and M. A. Yaman, "Smart controlling for traffic light time," 2017 IEEE Jordan Conference on Applied Electrical Engineering and Computing Technologies (AEECT), Aqaba, 2017, pp. 1-5, doi:10.1109/AEECT.2017.8257768.
- [5] Renjith Soman "Traffic Light Control and Violation Detection Using Image Processing". "IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN), vol. 08, no. 4, 2018, pp. 23-27
- [6] A. Kanungo, A. Sharma and C. Singla, "Smart traffic lights switching and traffic density calculation using video processing," 2014 Recent Advances in Engineering and Computational Sciences (RAECS), Chandigarh, 2014, pp. 1-6, doi:10.1109/RAECS.2014.6799542
- [7] Siddharth Srivastava, Subhadeep Chakraborty, Raj Kamal, Rahil, Minocha, "Adaptive traffic light timer controller", IIT KANPUR, NERDMAGAZINE
- [8] Ms. Saiili Shinde, Prof. Sheetal Jagtap, Vishwa Karma Institute of Technology, Intelligent traffic management system: a Review, IJIRST 2016